

CHESS SETUP: STEP 5

we wish you a happy and efficient 2019

Welcome to our 5th newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading

The European project investigating buildings' energy self-sufficiency

5th CHESS SETUP meeting in Sant Cugat

CHESS SETUP partners gathered in Sant Cugat this December to present the work done during this last year, the advances in the three pilots, and the next steps planned.

Furthermore, taking advantage of the organized meeting, the partners visited the works in execution. In this visit, Sant Cugat explained the status of the pilot and its development.

CHESS SETUP pilots

Lavola's headquarters

In Manlleu, CHESS SETUP system is being installed. During this last few months, the existing photovoltaic panels (PV) have been relocated and the new PV panels installed.

Furthermore, the hydraulic system and the concrete foundation are prepared for the heat pump implementation.

During the following weeks, the installation of the heat pump and the implementation of the monitoring and control system will take place.

Lavola pilot

Sant Cugat

In the Spanish sport centre, the construction phase began in September 2018; the works are being executed as scheduled and are planned to finish during the first week of March 2019. The last milestones achieved were the installation of the 160 PV-T panels and the reinforcement of the pavement where the thermal energy storage tank (TEST) will be installed.

Corby

At the end of December 2018, the drainage and the rear access road of the block properties have been built, the installation of boreholes for the Earth Energy Bank (EBB) and the foundations for the first 4 homes.

In January 2019, the block and beam flooring are going to be installed in order to erect the panelized wall system. Also, will be made the foundations for the next set of new homes.

Sant Cugat pilot

Corby pilot

Online & Offline

Website cumulative number of visitors

A year of incredible growth

2018 has been a year of huge impact and growth for our online communication tools.

The number of CHESS SETUP website's visitors has increased by 90% compared to the previous year.

In addition, our Twitter account has almost doubled the number of followers during this year, achieving 270 followers.

Website updated

Recently, the project's website has been deeply updated in order to target the visitors. The content and info on the project have been also updated according to the last advances and news of the pilots.

Lastly, a new section has been added to the Home page, which shows the real-time activity of the CHESS SETUP Twitter page.

Events and Conferences

During the year 2018, CHESS SETUP partners participated in more than 30 events, conferences and congresses. They introduced the project and its objectives, "the design and implementation of an efficient system able to supply heating and hot water in buildings from renewable sources" and spread the importance of working towards a sustainable society, achieving buildings self-sufficiency.

"To meet our climate goals, buildings need to use less energy and simultaneously enable a low-carbon grid by avoiding high and erratic peak energy demands. Why? Because buildings are the linchpin to a decarbonized grid – and the grid is only as green as buildings enable it to be."
Cara Carmichael, Rocky Mountain Institute

In the last months...

Smart City Expo World Congress 2018

On November 13th to 15th, the SCEWC 2018 gathered, in Barcelona (Spain), institutions, experts and high representatives of cities all around the world to discuss smart city sectors and urban innovations towards social and environmental sustainability. CHESS SETUP was there, represented by various partners.

CONAMA 2018

Madrid welcomed the 14th edition of the Environmental National Congress, CONAMA 2018, from 26th to 29th of November. It has become the environmental event of reference in Spain for the content quality, the high level of participation and the variety of professional profiles and environmental sectors represented.

Coming soon...

Horizon 2020 Energy Efficiency info day

The event will take place on Tuesday 22 January 2019 at Charlemagne building, in Brussels. Energy efficiency topics of the 2019 call of Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 3 – Clean, Secure and Efficient Energy – will be presented in a series of workshops organised by EASME throughout the day. The aim of the Horizon 2020 Energy Efficiency Info Day is to present funding opportunities under the 2019 call, to attract new applicants and potential beneficiaries, and to foster networking between participants.

International Conference on Renewable Energy ICREN 2019

The next in the series of the International Conference on Renewable Energy is the ICREN2019 focusing on international participation including experienced and young researchers with interest in renewable energy studies.

The conference will be held at the UNESCO Headquarters in Paris, France providing an unsurpassed venue to nurture debate in this globally important area. ICREN2019 will include articles and presentation on the latest research on renewable energy technologies, grid interactions, energy efficiency, data analytics, economics and finance, environmental and social impact as well as policy and climate change implications.

ABOUT THE PROJECT

For more information about the project, you can find us on,

- Our [webpage](#)
- Our Twitter account [@ChessSetup](#)
- Our [LinkedIn](#) page

Comparte via:

<http://www.chess-setup.net>